

Implementing Problem-Based Learning Model for Elevator Spare Part Procurement Planning in a Group of Airport Buildings

Tanutta Klongakara, Wuttinan Nunkaew

Department of Industrial Engineering, Thammasat School of Engineering, Thammasat University, Thailand

Email: tanuttak@gmail.com, nwuttinan@enr.tu.ac.th

Abstract

This paper proposes a framework of elevator spare part procurement planning decision in a group of airport buildings based on a Problem-based Learning (PBL) model. According to the lack of experience of newly graduated engineers in this field, they could not efficiently determine procurement planning concerning the yearly budget and several related factors. By organising a group of brainstorming team and applying the PBL model, newly graduated engineers have practised on procurement planning and discussed with a team of senior engineers who have more experiences in this field. The main discussion process has great benefits not only for junior engineers but also for senior engineers who can get some new points of view to creating the solution. The crucial criteria for elevator spare parts procurement planning, obtained from group brainstorming meetings and the PBL model, have been listed as the cost of spare parts purchasing, the lifetime of spare parts, the delivery lead times, and the warehousing management. These criteria were concluded in the procurement framework resulting in an enhanced performance of procurement planning as well as the reduction of workflow.

Keywords: Problem-Based Learning; Elevators Spare Parts; Brainstorm; Procurement Framework.

1 Introduction

Over the past few years, everyone has been keeping an eye on the tourism industries. The recent increase of tourists is a good guarantee of the growth of this sector. Airports of Thailand company limited (AOT), the state-owned enterprise, has operated as a state-commerce service provider for aviation business services. According to AOT's report (2018) and its overall business performance, the increase in the number of flights has also resulted in the increasing number of passengers utilizing the airports. Don Mueang International Airport (DMK) is one of the airports operated by AOT and provides facilities, high-efficiency technology and international standard security systems, this increases the ability of the airport to provide the airlines and passengers with uninterrupted services and high-quality operations. The preparation of the accessible equipment is a key responsibility of the maintenance department. Crucially, the equipment maintenance tasks require systematic planning. Maximising management means achieving the maintenance goal which is the ability to maintain the good condition of equipment and prevent damage, to provide them with the availability for service at all times, to prolong the service life, and to minimise cost. With regard to the elevator equipment, the spare parts inventory needed for maintenance process should be ready for emergency situations such as the case of elevator failure which could happen any time.

The maintenance department has many responsibilities such as planning of maintenance strategy, warehouse control, inventory management and procurement of spare parts. The equipment of elevators are quite complex because they have more details to pay attention to than other industrial machines (Moeuf, Pellerin, Lamouri, Tamayo-Giraldo, & Barbaray 2018). The maintenance department operates 24 hours daily and the staffs need to have proper maintenance preparation which would enable them to work against the clock to meet the strict deadline. Other important issues are the difficulties of the work since the equipment can be complex and various in kinds. Moreover, their lifetimes are different. There are various models and brands of the equipment and the government's procurement processes are time-consuming and comprise of many steps. Therefore, the maintenance requires those who are specialised or experienced to work in this field since they are familiar with the nature of the work to make proper and efficient decisions with regard to the elevator maintenance process. Since the demand of new graduated engineers with several skills are higher than the past, the newly graduated

engineers should take the opportunity to learn from their seniors and expert teams to gain different skills needed in the industry (ERASMUS+ CBHE PROJECT, 2019). According to the empirical study from Singha, Devikaa, Thiedeb, & Singh (2019), the skills that the newly graduated engineers need the most are expertise skills relating to fast learning abilities. The process of spare parts procurement planning from maintenance viewpoints can be improved by using new technologies of equipment such as a new remote maintenance system (Yamashita, Nakamura, Sakai, Fukata, & Sekine, 2017). This new device can utilise technology to help the equipment work more efficiently. However, in the case of elevator maintenance in the airport, the elevator parts are usually old and in need of changes. Maintenance tasks need an approval from the department of state budget in advance which can be time consuming. For all of these reasons, the maintenance team should aim to develop the skills of new graduated engineers by applying some PBL steps which focus on the results of the learning process and problem analysis to speed up the procurement planning process and to create criteria framework from the application of the PBL model.

2 Maintenance Strategy for Spare Part Planning

Several complex factors can be found within the procurement planning process. Maintenance team should concern as much as they can to cover all of the factors that affect the procurement plan. Complex maintenance tasks often involve the replacement of old parts with more modern parts to make the device work more efficiently. It is usually project-based and the problem would not recur. The most common maintenance strategy is preventive, subdividing the maintenance tasks under the right maintenance strategies. Parts are usually not be replaced until they are unable to operate (breakdown). Under preventive maintenance strategies, the goal is to replace parts before the failure and this depends on the policy of the team and the types of machine in question. The subdividing of maintenance tasks is the right choice for deteriorating parts such as electronic device for deteriorating-resistant parts. It is especially useful to follow preventive maintenance strategies. Arts (2013) refers to the maintenance guidelines and states that the internal device maintenance is different from the maintenance caused by customer usages in which the maintenance tasks often require many resources. The most important resources are:

- Experts, technicians, engineers or other trained professionals
- Tools and device
- Spare parts

Maintenance strategy is crucial with regard to the spare parts planning. Maintenance strategies determine when parts or equipment must be changed or maintained. In this subsection, we focus on maintenance/replacement decisions. Our case study suggests that the replacement of specific parts is more efficient than changing the entire body of the machine. Figure 1 provides an overview of maintenance strategies (Arts, 2013).

Figure 1. An overview of maintenance strategies.

In addition to choosing the right maintenance strategy for the policy and equipment, it is important to choose the right as well as experienced persons to make decisions in the process since the task requires expertise. Since the experts and senior teams are aware of this problem, they search for ways to teach useful skills to newly graduated engineers while at the same time finding the problems within elevator spare part procurement planning process by creating a framework of spare parts decision-making steps. (Driessen, Arts, Van Houtum, Rustenburg, & Huisman, 2015). The creation of this framework is done by experts and senior teams who are responsible for the planning procurement process such as the maintenance engineers, the inventory control team, the purchase team, and the high-level managers who are the final decision-makers. The team meeting has been joined by those who participate in the decision concerning the purchase of spare parts. These comprise of:

- Maintenance Manager, being on duty for 18 years, taking care of the budget of the whole department and making purchasing approvals before the decisions arrive at the unit of finance and accounting,
- Senior Mechanical Engineer, being on duty for 10 years, supervising the normal maintenance work and approving the job offers from Senior Maintenance operator,
- Site Operation Manager, being on duty for 28 years, responsible for controlling the budget for procurement, proposing procurement and controlling of spare parts,
- Finance and Accounting Manager, being on duty for 13 years, approving the procurement budget for maintenance work,
- Senior Maintenance Operator, being on duty for 30 years, following the preventive and emergency maintenance plans and working on the inventory issues.

As shown in this process flow diagram (Figure 2), the delay in the procurement process occurs during the procurement planning step which requires the highly experienced and skillful staffs as listed above to make purchasing decisions. In this case, It is not enough to pass on knowledge from experts to new staffs in order for the latter to be able to take full responsibility for the work instead. This is due to the complex nature of spare parts which vary in types. In order to avoid any problem within the procurement process, only those who have thorough mechanical knowledge of elevator systems as well as those with long working experience within the finance department could perform these procurement planning tasks.

Figure 2. The overall procurement process flow diagram.

3 Inventory Management

Determining the needs of spare parts is an important action that leads to successful operations and prevents the shutdown of machine service. In the case of improper inventory storage such as a storage with insufficient parts, this could badly affect the operation. This also indicates ineffective purchasing plans. In general, when considering the obtainment of each spare part, there are several factors that one must take into account. The factors are summarized as follows:

- Number of usages of each machine model
- Machine life
- The number of spare parts usages in the past
- The number of spare parts inventories
- Spare parts supply period
- Working conditions of other machines that are necessary for the operation

The whole supply chain depends on the flow process of materials and information. The main concept of the

SCMs is about the cooperation and the reduction of inventory in the chain system. The continual planning can be divided into the flow of process. Figure 3 shows a form of inventory management in which the components of the chain operate independently and the data is transferred at the level of adjacent links (Krzyżniak S., 2005).

Figure 3. Streams in inventory management.

The arrows in Figure 3 clearly indicate the links between each process, giving the information about the nodes displayed in the order-size dependent on retailers' audits. The same demand levels are repeated as shown in the order from other departments in the chain, and each link is only for their own benefit. The close relationship between suppliers and customers leads to a specific inventory level being maintained on each process. This is kept in the "ready to ship" section in order to meet the demand of customers at all times. Therefore, the safety stock is necessary for mitigating risk of stockouts caused by uncertainties in the demand while the independent creation of each process is caused by the creation of excess inventory throughout the supply chain. In order to commit to the high-standard level of customer service, most companies must control the cost and other overhead expenses, having appropriate warehouse management and adequate stock of spare parts. The accumulation of the overhead cost in each process of supply chain comes from the manufacturer, the supplier, the wholesaler or retailer who strive to take appropriate measures to anticipate their product demand. At the same time, each process has its own role in supporting the main objective which is the assurance of achieving maximum customer service level. In this step, several questions arise from the issues of the limitation of demand and from the demand analysis. The answers to these questions will help adjust the company's operations to be in accordance with the real demands and help forecast forward to predict the costs that may incurred due to the warehouse overstocking of unsold products. Kot, Grondys, & Szopa (2011) have mentioned the existence of predictive techniques which exist in the advanced IT systems used for warehouse management. In this case, however, one cannot apply these techniques for the operation in some limited areas. The reason for controlling the level of spare parts is not only about the issue of the inventory cost but also about the management of spare part inventory.

At the present, the processes of the procurement of elevator spare parts are grouped according to the physical and functional parts of each item. There are 3 groups as followed:

- Group A is a group of the main parts which have the characteristics and main functions of propulsion system, with high value and long-lasting service life. They are made to order. Usually, there is a plan to change these parts according to their service life cycle to prevent the breakdown of devices (BM, Breakdown Maintenance) such as the main rope, the main controller, and the buffer.
- Group B is a group of moving parts with normal use. They have a short lifespan and average market price. These items can be replaced where the replacement plan is in accordance with the maintenance history. These parts include the door chain and the door sensor.
- Group C is a group of parts which have the characteristics of being in direct contact with the users. They are usually cheap in price but can greatly affect the safety of the users. They are used very frequently and have the more frequent replacement cycle. The spare parts are installed when necessary according to the daily check. These parts include lighting device and floor buttons.

The diverse types of inventory of elevator parts means that the management requires an expertise and the right decision for procuring a list of spare part that can be used when needed as the delay in obtaining the parts could affect the image and the level of service of the airport.

4 PBL Model

Problem-based learning (PBL) is the common method of teaching that helps solve complex real-world problems. It is a tool that promotes the learners to learn concepts and principles as opposed to direct presentations of facts and concepts, Alves et al., (2016) said that the problem was solved by challenges faced to it. The PBL model can be applied to develop problem-solving skills, critical thinking skills, and communication skills. In addition, it provides opportunities for working in groups, searching and evaluating materials for research purposes, and lifelong learning (Duch, Groh, & Allen, 2001).

PBL could be integrated into any learning situation. The qualitative approach for several data concerned by collective techniques for example focus group, interview, literature review or specialist's opinion. You also can use PBL creating evaluation lists and the main topics connecting these various uses are real-world issues. The key success is using focus group technique with include a brainstorm process. Investigation of details in factors and problem process is more interactive and share a point of view which involves the roots of problem. Therefore, PBL has adapted to renew in upper level education and provide a case study assessment of learning (Christie & de Graaff, 2017).

According to Duch, Groh, & Allen (2001), any type of research can benefit from PBL method. While the main concerns will vary among disciplines, there are some characteristics of PBL that this research can adapt in the case study. By following PBL method, the arguments chosen for the discussions should require newly graduated engineers to make rational decisions and develop logical thinking, connecting what are being discussed with their past experience and knowledge. The problems discussed should be complex enough so that the newly graduated engineers must work together as a team to solve them. A main concept or idea is to be chosen for the discussion, which will be followed by the assignment or homework that are assigned to them. The ideas and problems under consideration are that of the real-world situations. It is important to develop the aspects of storytelling or other creative practices as to increase the motivation of the new engineers in solving the problems. More complex problems will challenge them to work harder. All the available resources should be used. The problems discussed need to be introduced step-by-step so that new engineers can specifically identify the issues that would lead them closer to their goals. (Ribas, 2009) Experts and seniors should help guide the new engineers by using the problem-solving model during the meeting. Both group discussions and small group work should be reported. The final step is for the new engineers to identify important resources and learn to use these resources themselves. Nevertheless, it will be useful if the seniors help identify some resources and lead them at the beginning.

Steps of Problem-Based Learning are described as follows: (Center for Teaching, 2020). Step 1: Exploring the problems, learning the concepts, principles, and necessary information as well as new skills regarding the proposed topic. Step 2: Within a group meeting, creating a list of what they already know about the situation. Step 3: Defining the problems, putting them in a scope of what is already known, and informing what the new engineers expect to learn. Step 4: Researching on the information and find resources that will help create compelling arguments. Step 5: Checking other solutions for possible actions and look for better solutions, determining and testing possible hypotheses. Step 6: Offering and supporting the selected solution, with the conclusions being clearly identified and supported, along with relevant information and evidence. Step 7: Checking the performance, an important step in developing your problem-solving skills. Students must evaluate their performance and make some improvements for future problems. These steps which are applied during the on-site work and the insights from the analysis will help the new engineers to understand things better by having a meeting with the experts. This allows them to share ideas together (Hernández et al., 2015).

5 Research Methodology

The newly graduated engineers should be self-taught to understand the work processes. On the first day, the company's general knowledge and the special knowledge relevant to the job will be informed. It is the responsibility of the senior team and yourself. There are clear steps which can be studied on the e-learning platform or from face-to-face meetings. In this case, the PBL procedure goes into effect with the annual purchasing and planning solution as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The work procedures.

The first step in the procedures is that of the introduction of the framework and scope of each sector's responsibilities with regard to the whole process. The new engineers are informed of how the procurement process is done, as well as on how the yearly procurement plan is created. Within the maintenance sector, the seniors are responsible as the instructors of the newly graduated engineers who are taught on the site following the concept of on-the-job training (OJT) since more benefits can be reaped from such practice due to the availability of equipment and other useful resources needed for an effective learning. After this stage, the senior engineers would encourage the newly graduated engineers to identify problems and search for possible obstacles that could derive from the procurement process. Those who have questions with regard to what they have learned at the beginning will have a chance to ask for clarifications and then move the meeting onto the next stage, in which the junior engineers will hear from their seniors the evaluation of problems gathered from the previous stage. The seniors will give suggestions, identify existing limitations, and clarify on some points that are not clear from the beginning. This significantly reduces the time of the whole learning process. Due to the fact that some aspects of the work have limitations and problems that require specific ways to resolve them, the new engineers can learn a lot from the expertise of the seniors who are more experienced. After gaining some feedbacks, if the new engineers have some more questions to ask, they will be given the time to research and study more before moving on to the next stage which is that of a group discussion. In this stage, all will brainstorm and find key factors within the procurement process as to create the criteria framework which is to be used as a tool in improving the spare parts procurement process. The effective outcome of the meeting can be created with the participation of those who have experienced the real-world working situations

as well as the new engineers who might possibly add some interesting insights that are not normally acknowledged by the senior engineers.

5.1 Process Work Flow

From the problem analysis process during the meeting, the main problem which can be observed is the delay in the procurement planning of elevator spare parts. The meeting provided the opportunity for new engineers to participate in solving the problems and exchanging ideas by adapting PBL model and learning from real-world problems. According to the brainstorming session, one issue suggested that the problem of the planning and decision-making process concerning the purchase of spare parts can be time-consuming. Many factors should be taken into consideration and the insights from the experts in this field can be useful for helping the new engineers gain expertise in this matter. From the meeting, a new engineer suggested that a procurement factors criteria framework should be created to reduce the working time spent by those who work in the sector. This framework can be used in the future teaching session so that the new engineers will be able to work more efficiently.

5.2 Criteria Framework

In the brainstorming session and group discussions including the managers, the senior engineers, and newly graduated engineers, resulted in the framework and planning of the procurement of elevator spare parts. The important criteria for the planning for the purchase of elevator spare parts are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Criteria framework for elevator’s spare part procurement planning

Criteria	Definition	Factors	Definition
Cost of spare parts purchasing	Price of Spare parts which is the direct cost of company.	Standard price / market price	Spare part price is found in market or last price within 2 years.
		Warranty	The spare part warranty period is confirmed by buyer to guarantee their product. To deal with our company, warranty period at least 1 year, followed by a term of reference.
		Number of spare parts	Number of parts installed/ the purchasing volume
A lifetime of spare parts	Spare part life span from manual and usage life times when start use.	Frequency of elevators use	Elevator locations impact the frequency of the usage which inturn affects the life-span of the parts
		The chage of spare parts in maintenance period plan	Spare part purchasing without concern about spare part condition. Changing follows maintenance plan.
Delivery lead times	Delivery time starts from the time contract is signed till the arrival of the spare parts	Manufacture production plan	Type of production and warehouse strategy of manufacture (made to order or ready to ship)
Warehousing management	The management of spare parts by the maintenance team (buyer)	Budget	Budget for the purchase of spare parts each time
		Spare parts and their effects on elevator safety	Types of spare parts that affect the safety of the users
		Urgent demand	Sellers must have the safety stock Urgent demand in case breakdown of equipment/ its effect on spare part delivery

The criteria framework which affects the procurement planning process can be categorised into 4 groups which are the cost of spare part purchasing, a lifetime of spare parts, the delivery lead time, and warehousing management. Each group has its own factors, all of which determine the nature of the complex and

important planning process. So far, only those with experiences in this field or the experts are able to take into consideration all of the dimensions of these related factors. They make decisions within the spare parts procurement planning using statistical data analysis which means mistakes are unlikely to occur. However, this criteria framework, which is the result of the utilisation of PBL steps, greatly facilitated the brainstorming session and increased its efficiency. The maintenance team has asked the new engineers to apply this criteria framework on the case study. The result was that they could now understand all the dimensions of the problems and all the factors which must be taken into account, leading to the speed-up of the procurement planning process.

6 Conclusion and Recommendation

The on-site problem-solving process can be applied by the PBL steps which are useful both for the experts, the seniors, and the new engineers who are given opportunities to share their knowledges and experiences. According to the analysis, the presented criteria framework mentioned in this research can be utilized as a tool to facilitate and enhance the quality of planning process concerning the procurement of elevator's spare parts. The proposed framework can also be applied to similar cases such as elevator equipment, the cost of spare parts procurement, spare part lifetime, shipping lead time, and warehouse management. In addition, the learning process based on the PBL steps is also effective at solving more complex problems and can be adapted to new situations.

For the further study, an Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and a Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) will be utilized to enhance the operational planning issues such as specific expertise and personal experience which are related to quality factors.

Acknowledgement

This publication is the partial outcome of the project "Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE4.0)" that has been funded with support from the European Commission (Project Number: 586137-EPP-1-2017-1-TH-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP). The authors also would like to acknowledge the support from the Thammasat School of Engineering, Thammasat University, Thailand.

This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

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